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Macroeconomic Policy And Poverty Alleviation In Nigeria: A Case Study Of CBN's POS Cashless Policy Operation In Edjebah, Warri, Delta State

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ABSTRACT

This study examines the effect of the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) cashless policy operationalized through Point of Sale (POS) terminals on poverty alleviation in Delta State, Nigeria, with specific focus on POS operators in Edjeba, Warri. Anchored on Empowerment Theory, the research investigates whether POS operations have contributed to poverty reduction through job creation, income generation, and enhanced financial inclusion. A descriptive survey research design was adopted. From a population of 200 POS operators, a sample of 200 respondents was used using population sample. Data were collected using a validated 20-item on a 4 Likert scale questionnaire and analyzed with Chi-square and t-test statistics at the 0.05 level of significance.. Findings reveal that POS operations alleviate poverty and create jobs to a very high extent, increase income generation to a high extent, and promote financial inclusion to a high extent among operators. Hypothesis testing shows a significant gender difference in perceptions regarding poverty alleviation and job creation while no significant gender differences were found for income generation, and financial inclusion. The study concludes that the CBN's POS-driven cashless policy functions as a practical empowerment mechanism by enabling self-employment, steady income streams, and broader access to financial services. It recommends intensified awareness, capacity building, and policy support to deepen POS adoption and maximize its poverty-reducing potential.

Keywords: cashless policy, poverty alleviation, financial inclusion

INTRODUCTION

The existence of multi-dimensional and extreme poverty in a country like Nigeria that is well-endowed with abundant resources is a critical challenge that needs to be addressed urgently. The need to immediately arrest this monster called poverty stems largely from the fact it has adverse implications, not only on human wellbeing, but also on the overall socio-economic fabric of Nigeria. In other words, because poverty has deleterious impacts on human wellbeing, its alleviation and total eradication has been identified as an ethical, social, political and economic imperative to human kind (Ayo, 2022). The government plays an essential role in the fight against poverty, mainly through the use of macroeconomic policy framework. The cashless policy is one of such macroeconomic policy reforms, that Nigeria, through the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) has introduced to revolutionize the face of financial transactions and has opened another chapter in the Nigerian banking system which aimed at modernizing the financial sector, increasing transparency and enhancing overall efficiency in the economy. According to the CBN (2023), the cashless policy is to discourage the use of huge raw cash for transactions, but encourages the use of bank transfer, ATM Card, POS and other financial instruments for transferring cash in transactions which will decreasing the amount of physical cash in

circulation and promote electronic transactions for payments, transfers, and other financial activities, but not completely eliminating cash.

Statement of problem

Poverty remains perhaps, one of the greatest challenges bedeviling Nigeria as a country as economic growth recorded in many years of oil boom has failed to impact the lives of the ordinary Nigerians as reflected in the unemployment level which remains very high and per capita income (PCI) very low, below the globally tolerable and expected thresholds. Most social intervention programs in the past which were aimed at alleviating poverty and improving the lot of the vulnerable masses have been ineffective largely due to the activities of corrupt officials who don't allow the benefits of such schemes to trickle down to the poor citizenry. Experts are of the view that for the fight against poverty to be meaningful, there is the need to reduce human contact with intervention funds and policies thus the CBN introduced a macroeconomic policy called the Cashless Policy. Though the electronic banking adoption has significantly penetrated among the populace while the cashless policy has further spurred policy innovation that has expanded the breadth and depth of financial systems participants with increasing transaction channels and wider financial access points, the researcher wonders if the introduction of the Point of Sales (POS) which is a child of the cashless policy of the CBN has ensuring financial inclusion, provision of job opportunities for the army of unemployed youth and more importantly has it provided income-earning opportunities for the masses.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The study aims at examining and evaluating the macroeconomic policy and poverty alleviation in Nigeria using the CBN POS cashless policy operation in Edjeba as its case study. Specifically, the study intends to:

- i. To examine the effect of POS cashless policy and poverty alleviation.
- iii. To examine the effect of the POS cashless policy on job creation.
- iv. To examine the effect of the POS cashless policy on income generation.
- v. To examine the extent the POS operations have created financial inclusion.

Research Questions

The following are the research question that guides this study:

1. Is there a relationship between gender and the extent POS cashless policy alleviates poverty in Edjeba?
2. Is there a relationship between gender and the extent POS cashless policy created jobs?
3. Is there a relationship between gender and the extent POS cashless policy increased income generation?
4. Is there a relationship between gender and the extent POS cashless policy resulted in financial inclusion

Research Hypotheses

The following are the hypotheses of this study:

- H0₁: There is no significant relationship between gender and the extent POS cashless policy alleviates poverty in Edjebah.
- H0₂: There is no significant relationship between gender and the extent POS cashless policy on job creation in Ejebah.
- H0₃: There is no significant relationship between gender and the extent POS cashless policy on income generation in Ejebah
- H0₄: There is no significant relationship between gender and the extent POS cashless policy on financial inclusion in Ejebah.

Delimitation of the Study

The study is delimited to POS operators in Edjaba, Warri, Delta State to Investigate how POS cashless policy implantation in Nigeria has alleviated poverty, created job opportunities for the teeming population, how it has resulted in income generation and also enhanced financial inclusion for the operators of the POS business in Warri. The respondents of this study was limited to operators of POS business in Edjaba, Warri South Local Government Area of Delta State.

METHODOLOGY

The research design adopted by the researcher is the descriptive survey design. The population of study is 200 POS operators in Ejebah Warri comprising of 122 females and 78 male while the sample of the study is 200 using the population sample sampling technique and stratified in to male and female. The instrument for data collection was a 20 item survey survey scale titled “Macroeconomic policies and poverty alleviation in Nigeria (MPPAN)” and oral interview which was administered on subject of this study and interview conducted on same. The content and construct validity of the research instrument was determined by (3) three experts in the field of Economics, Measurement and Evaluation and Psychology respectively, from University of Porthacourt. The test re-test method was adopted to determine the reliability of the research instrument and a reliability coefficient of 0.76 was gotten which indicated that the instrument was reliable enough to be used for this study. Chi-square () was used to analyze the data to answer the research questions while t- test was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of statistical significance.

RESULTS

Research questions

Research question 1: *Is there a relationship between gender and the extent POS cashless policy alleviates poverty in Edjeba?*

Hypothesis H₀₁

There is no significant relationship between gender and the extent POS cashless policy alleviates poverty in Edjebah.

Table 1: Gender and the use of POS to alleviates poverty Cross tabulation

		The use of POS to alleviates poverty									
		VLE		LE		HE		VHE		Total	
		N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
Gender	Male	0	0.0%	12	60.0%	20	26.0%	27	27.0%	59	29.5%
	Female	3	100.0%	8	40.0%	57	74.0%	73	73.0%	141	70.5%
	Total	3	100.0%	20	100.0%	77	100.0%	100	100.0%	200	100.0%

From the above table, 12 male and 8 female respondents said POS cashless policy of the CBN alleviates poverty to a Low Extent (LE) respectively. Again 20 male and 57 male rooted for High Extent (HE); while 27 of male and 73 female respondents opined that POS cashless policy of the CBN alleviates poverty to a Very High Extent (VHE). However, no male respondent favored Very low Extent (VLE) except 3 female.

Table 2: summary of chi sq analysis on response of male and female POS operators on POS cashless policy on poverty alleviation.

	Value	Df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	10.962 ^a	3	.012
Likelihood Ratio	10.846	3	.013
N of Valid Cases	200		

Decision rule:

If $p < 0.05$ = there is a significant relationship/ difference

If $p > 0.05$ there is no significant relationship/ difference

On poverty alleviation, the total number of male and female POS operators is 200. The chi sq calculated value is 10.962 using 3 degree of freedom, a significant value of 0.013 at 0.05 level of significance is obtained. At 0.05 alpha level, 0.013 significant value and 10.962 calculated value, shows that there is a significant relationship/difference between gender and the extent POS cashless policy alleviates poverty in Edjebah.

Research Question 2: *Is there a relationship between gender and the extent POS cashless policy created jobs?*

Hypothesis H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between gender and the extent POS cashless policy on job creation in Ejebah.

Table 3: Genders and Job Creation Cross tabulation

		Job Creation								Total	
		VLE		LE		HE		VHE			
		N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%		
Gender	Male	1	16.7%	18	51.4%	20	25%	15	15.7%	68	34%
	Female	5	83.3%	17	48.5%	57	75%	80	84.2%	132	66%
	Total	6	100.0%	22	100.0%	77	100.0%	95	100.0%	200	100.0%

*The scale of measurement for table 1 applies

On job creation, 1 male respondents and 5 female respondents respectively favored Very low Extent (VLE) on the extent to which the POS cashless policy of the government has created jobs. 18 male respondents and 17 female respondents respectively ticked low Extent (LE), while 20 male and 57 female respectively responded to the questionnaire item High Extent (HE). Furthermore, 15 male and 80 female were in support of Very High Extent (VHE) questionnaire item

Table 4: Summary of Chi-square analysis on the response of male and female POS operators on the POS cashless policy on job creation

	Value	Df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	11.462 ^a	3	.015
Likelihood Ratio	11.335	3	.015
N of Valid Cases	200		

*The scale of measurement for table 1 applies

The total number of male and female POS operators is 200. The chi sq calculated value of 11.462 using 3 degree of freedom, a significant value of 0.010 at 0.05 level of significance is obtained. At 0.05 alpha level, 0.015 significant value and 11.462 calculated value, the null hypothesis is reject and conclude that there is a significant relationship/difference between gender and the extent POS cashless policy increase job creation in Ejebah.

Research question 3: *Is there a relationship between gender and the extent POS cashless policy increased income generation?*

Hypothesis H₀₃: There is no significant relationship between gender and the extent POS cashless policy on income generation in Ejebah.

Table 5: Gender and Increase in Income Generation Cross tabulation

		Increase in Income Generation				Total	
		HE		VHE			
		N	%	N	%		
Gender	Male	35	27.3%	24	33.3%	59	29.5%
	Female	93	72.7%	48	66.7%	141	70.5%
	Total	128	100.0%	72	100.0%	200	100.0 %

The Cross tabulation table above revealed that 35 male and 93 female responded that the POS cashless policy of the government has increased income generation to High Extent (HE). While 24 male and 48 female response from the research instrument indicated that POs cashless of the government has increase income generation to a Very High Extent (VHE).

Table 6: summary of chi sq analysis of the difference in the response of male and female POS operators on the influence of POS cashless policy on income generation

	Value	Df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (1-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	.795 ^a	2	.373		
Continuity Correction ^b	.533	2	.465		
Likelihood Ratio	.787	2	.375		
Fisher's Exact Test				.420	.232
N of Valid Cases	200				

*The scale of measurement for table 1 applies

The Chi-Square value of 0.795 is not significant at $p= 0.373$ since this value is greater than $p= 0.05$ level of significance, thus we cannot reject H_0 and conclude that There is no significant relationship/difference between gender and the extent POS cashless policy increases income generation in Ejebah

Research question 4: *Is there a relationship between gender and the extent POS cashless policy resulted in financial inclusion?*

Hypothesis H_{04} : There is no significant relationship between gender and the extent POS cashless policy on financial inclusion in Ejebah.

Table 7: Gender and Financial Inclusion Cross tabulation

		Financial Inclusion						Total	
		LE		HE		VHE		N	%
Gender		N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
	Male	2	20.0%	49	32.9%	8	19.5%	59	29.5%
	Female	8	80.0%	100	67.1%	33	80.5%	141	70.5%
	Total	10	100.0%	149	100.0%	41	100.0%	200	100.0%

*The scale of measurement for table 1 applies

Data from table 9 presents the scale in response of male and female POs operators on the extent to which POS cashless policy of CBN has brought about financial inclusion. 2 male respondents and 8 female respondents opined that it has increased financial inclusion to a low extent (LE) while 49 male respondents and 100 female respondents respectively rooted that it has to a high extent (HE) increase financial inclusion. However, 8 male respondents and 33 female respondents respectively indicated that the POS cashless policy resulted in financial inclusion to a very high extent (VHE).

Table 8: summary of chi sq analysis of the difference in the response of male and female POS operators on the influence of POS cashless policy on financial inclusion

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	3.222 ^a	2	.200
Likelihood Ratio	3.403	2	.182
N of Valid Cases	200		

The Chi-Square value of 3.222 with $df= 3$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.200$ is not significant at $p= 0.05$ level of significance. Consequently, we cannot reject the null hypothesis (H_0); but to conclude that there is no significant relation/difference in the responses of male and female POS operators on the influence of POS cashless policy on financial inclusion in Warri.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The finding of this study indicates that POS cashless policy of CBN has brought about the alleviation of people from poverty in Edjebah. This finding is consistent with a body of knowledge from other research who suggest that the introduction of the POS cashless policy of the CBN which brought

about the introduction of the POS machine has resulted to the creation of jobs which generates income for millions of Nigeria, thereby reducing the prevailing numbers of people face with the daily challenge of meeting daily basic necessities. Furthermore, both male and female POS operators did not have a common view on the contribution of POS cashless policy on poverty alleviation this was so due to the fact that the females constitute a greater share of the respondents and as such their views out weight those of the male respondents. Thus the finding suggests female POS operators perceive greater poverty alleviation benefits from POS cashless policy than their male counterpart.

Also, the finding of this study indicates that POS cashless policy of CBN has brought about the creation of job opportunity for many in Edjebah. This finding corroborates with empirical evidences from other research that insist that the introduction of the use of POS as a result of the Cashless policy of the CBN has initiated open doors for the creation of job opportunity not just only because of the ease of entry but also the minimum capital requirements which does not only alleviate people from poverty but also further allows for diversification and combination with other business due to the flexible nature of its operation. Furthermore, the male and female POS operators did not have a common view on the contribution of POS cashless policy on job creation this was so due to the fact that the females constitute a greater share of the respondents and as such their views out weight those of the male respondents. Thus the findings suggests female POS operators acknowledge the POS cashless policy as a window for job creation through the POs operation.

Again, the finding of this study indicates that POS cashless policy of CBN has brought about increase in income generation to individuals who operate POS. This finding is in line with other related research work that collectively postulates that the small business acceptance of payment through a wider range of option such as transfer of cash and use of ATM as against the tradition method of cash only for transactions from customers has improved the ease of transaction and convenience offered to clients which in turn dives up sale resulting to high turnover rates and profit accumulation. Although, female appears numerically higher in both category, which is largely attributed to them having a greater share of the respondents, the slight differences observed between male and female responses was not strong enough to be considered meaningful to influence the view on how POS cashless policy results to income generation for POS operators. Thus the findings suggests both male and female POS operators acknowledge the POS cashless policy as a means to increase income through POS operation.

Finally, the finding of this study indicates that POS cashless policy of CBN has brought about financial inclusion to small business owners who cannot due to their business size access financial facilities through POS cashless policy of CBN. This finding is supported by the related empirical studies that opines that the introduction of POS cashless policy which birth the use of POS has made small business owners to build credible transaction history which could be leverage on to secure loans and investment from financial institutions to expand their business. These related studies also postulates that before the proliferation of POS machines and their agents, residence of rural areas barely have access to banking services but with the introduction of the Cashless policy by the CBN, mini bank branches have been set up in this rural areas with POS agents serving as their representatives. Although, female appears numerically higher in both category, which is largely attributed to them having a greater share of the respondents, the differences in response observed between male and female was not sufficient enough to be considered meaningful to influence the views on how POS cashless policy results to financial inclusion. Thus the findings suggests both male and female POS operators acknowledge the POS cashless policy as a means to increase financial inclusion through POS operation.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of the study, the discussion on the finding and the attendant economic implications, it is concluded that, the POS cashless policy of CBN has brought about poverty alleviation, job creation, increase in income generation and financial inclusion for POS operators.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Sensitization programmes should be organised to create more awareness to the populace on how the adoption of the Cashless policy CBN through the use of POS can alleviate people from poverty.
2. There should be enlightenment and creation of awareness by the CBN and other financial institution on the need to embrace POS cashless policy of CBN as means for job creation.
3. CBN through other relevant stake holder in financial sector should educate the populace on how increase in income is achievable through the use of POS by adopting the cashless policy of CBN.
4. There is need for the CBN in collaboration with other relevant financial institutions to continuously sensitize people on the need to embrace the POS cashless policy of the CBN to increase the reach of financial inclusion.

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